

Two Questions Dr. Michael H. Koplitz Bava Metzia 35A

(This is an explanation of what Modern Talmud Tales is all about. A modern-day scenario is presented. The reader is challenged to solve the issue using a particular section of the Talmud. In many cases, there is no right or wrong decision. However, you should be able to support your decision based on the Talmud tractate. The ancient way of life is often very different from today's ways. The challenge is understanding how the people in Judea solved their social problems.)

This section was a long tractate with two good questions to be pondered. Therefore, both are presented.

Fred created a loan with Mike in which he borrowed \$1000. Mike got on the internet and downloaded a promissory note template. The two men signed the note. They felt it was not necessary to go to the expense of notarizing it since they were friends. One day Fred was in the yard burning his trash when he noticed the promissory note was in the fire. How did it get there? He did not know this answer, but it was too late to save the note. It was gone. He told Mike about the loss of the note. Mike's greed took over he decided not to pay the loan. When Fred demanded his money back, Mike said he had no proof that a loan was ever made. Using Bava Metzia 35A, how would you rule?

Sam had purchased a \$15000 Rolex for his bride. However, he did not want to give it to her until their wedding anniversary months later. Therefore, he entrusted the Rolex to his good friend Pete. When the anniversary day came, Pete could not find the Rolex. Sam was furious and demanded some compensation. Pete gave him his 2010 Mustang GT with a book value of \$15,000. Six months later, Pete found the Rolex. By then, the Rolex had increased in value to \$16,000, and the car devalued to \$14,000. Pete said he would make the exchange only if Sam gave him \$2,000. A long argument resulted. Using

Bava Metzia 35A, how would you rule? Is it an even exchange to give back the car for the Rolex?

